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Hermeneutical discussion in Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā: with special reference to the suffix ktvā/lyap

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Abstract:

Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā (PM) is the science of sentence interpretation (vākyaārtha-śāstra). It discusses on various elements of a sentences in order to know its import. The modern science which deals with such aspect of interpretation is hermeneutics. The discussions in PM are hermeneutical in nature. In order to arrive at the understanding of import of a sentence, PM discusses various elements of a sentences, their construction and the construed meanings generating verbal understanding. One such element is the kṛt suffix ktvā/lyap which has been used in many prescriptive sentences of the Veda. This paper aims at discussing the hermeneutical discussions with respect to this suffix of ktvā/lyap in PM.

Keywords: Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā, kṛt, suffix, ktvā, lyap, hermeneutics, sentence meaning, import, interpretation.

Introduction

Suffixes are as much an integral part of a language as are case-endings and verb-forms and it is more so in case of Sanskrit language. Words formed by suffix additions are found in abundance in the texts of Sanskrit language. Word-forming suffixes in Sanskrit are mainly kṛt (primary) and taddhita (secondary). The kṛt (primary suffix) are important as they are an essential tool for forming primary words from the verbal root. These kṛt suffixes are used in many senses which are stated broadly by Pāṇini in his aphorism which are to some extent both prescriptive and regulatory in their uses. However, a true understanding of the same is only possible by observation of the various usages in the language. Thus, the determination of senses or rather the meaning that is understood by them may be varied as well as reciprocal of its function in that context.

Classification of words in Sanskrit

Words in Sanskrit language can be classified in many manners. One of the earliest classification of words is found in Nirukta of Yāska, the earliest lexicon of Sanskrit, giving etymological meaning of Vedic words.

Yāska divides words in Sanskrit into :

- i. Nāman – noun or substantive
- ii. Ākhyāta – verb
- iii. Upasarga – preposition, and
- iv. Nīpāta - particles

Pāṇini has a slightly different classification. In the words of Abhyankar¹

Pāṇini has used the term प्रातिपदिक for a substantive base without case affix, and the term धातु for a root without verb-ending. He has altogether left aside the ambiguous terms नामन् and आख्यात for which the words सुबन्त and तिङन्त were used by his commentators.

Pāṇini has mentioned the words उपसर्ग and निपात and defined them; but, for the purpose of his technique he has included both of them in the general category of subanta words. Emilie Aussant² in her various classification of words in Sanskrit has given one of the classifications based on the Pāṇinian model as follows:

The place of the suffix ktvā/lyap can be easily observed in the image of the chart above.

The suffix ktvā/lyap - Grammatical discussion

Pāṇini has prescribed suffixes applicable to verbal root in three basic senses of agent (kartṛ), object (karma) and action (bhava). However, in some cases suffixes are also added to denote other case endings. The suffix kṛt by default has been prescribed in the sense of agent (kartṛ)³ unless some other sense has been mentioned. Sometimes, the word formed from kṛt suffix are mostly noun, but sometimes these also form indeclinable.

One such krit suffix is the ktvā/lyap suffix. The Pāṇinian rule describing its usage is 'samānakartṛkayoḥ pūrvakāle'⁴ which Bhattojīdikshīt has explained as, 'samānakartṛkayor-dhatvarthayoḥ tatra pūrvakāle vidyamānāddhātoḥ ktvā syāt'⁵ i.e. amongst the verbs having the same agent, there is application of the suffix ktvā after the verb denoting the earlier time'. And it is used in the sense of denoting action (bhāva). This corresponds to the category of gerund in English language. The suffix ktvā is applied to roots not preceded by prefix (upāsarga), while the suffix lyap is applied to roots preceded by prefix other than the negative particle nañ⁶. The example stated in Siddhāntakaumudī is bhuktvā vrajati (having eaten he

goes). There are some other discussions regarding the construction of this suffix ktvā stating that the verbal form ending in the tiṅ is main (pradhāna) in the sentence and all the words ending in ktvā being subsidiary are construed in the main action and act as qualifiers of the same.

Hermeneutical science- Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā

Such being the grammatical discussions, there are other aspects too associated with this. These are the hermeneutical aspects. Every meaningful element of a language has a hermeneutical aspect attached to it. Hermeneutics the term chiefly denotes interpretation. In spite of the grammatical analyses of a sentence, every sentence has to be interpreted in order to get its true import when it is used in a context. The grammatical analyses alone is not sufficient to give complete import of a sentence. Thus, all the elements of a language must also be discussed for its hermeneutical aspects. This work has been done systematically by the philosophical system known as Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā, the aim of which is to interpret the Vedic sentences to know its import. At the time of discussion of various Vedic sentences, discussing the doubts that are raised and arriving at a definite conclusion regarding the exact meaning given by the sentences, thereby facilitating the correct performance of the rite prescribed by the Veda, the Mīmāṃsakas also discuss various elements that occur in the sentence and the true import of it. Such discussions are also found with respect to the suffix ktvā/lyap.

The suffix ktvā/lyap - Hermeneutical discussion

The suffix ktvā occurs in many Vedic sentences. A few of these are analyzed here for understanding the hermeneutical aspect associated with it. The most prominent discussion occurring about the suffix ktvā is with respect to the Vedic sentence, 'vedaṁ kṛtvā vediṁ karoti'⁷. The term veda is used for a kind of broom that is used in sacrificial rite. The term vedi is used for the demarcated space between the alters used for keeping the sacrificial materials. The sentence used here means, having prepared the veda the agent makes the vedi.

The import of this sentence is making known the order (krama) in the rite. So, the order intended by the Vedic sentences would be, first he makes the veda and then the vedi. The order (krama) is defined as, avyavahitottaratva-rūpam-ānantaryam (Bhaṭṭadīpikā 5.1.1) i.e. the proceeding having the form of being later which is not hindered by any other (occurrences). Thus, in this case, there should not be any other action performed between the two actions.

Now the question arises as to how does this injunction makes known the un-hindered part too? This is explained in the following way : Both the creation of the veda and

the vedi are known by the same injunction of performance (prayoga-vidhi). Thus there arises the necessity of performance of all the subsidiaries at the same time (sahānuṣṭhāna). If this injunction does not imply the order of performance, then there is problem of the injunction becoming redundant. Hence, in the injunction *vedaṁ kṛtvā vedīm karoti* the suffix *ktvā* making known the *pūrvakālatvam*-the state of being prior in general, makes known the part of un-hinderedness through secondary implication (*lakṣaṇā*). Hence the veda and vedi being known by other injunctions, the import of this whole injunction is making known the order through the suffix *ktvā*.

Other instances

There are other instances too where the suffix *ktvā* occurs. Significant among them is the sentence *darśapūrṇamāsābhyām iṣṭvā soma yajeta*⁸. Here too there is use of the suffix *ktvā*. However, there is no cognition of the part of un-hinderedness in order by this injunction. This is because, the performance of *darśapūrṇamāsa* and the performance of soma sacrifice are totally independent of each other. Hence there is no expectancy of the soma sacrifice of any kind of order with the *darśapūrṇamāsa*. Thus, this injunction does not make known the order. Then what is the import of this injunction? It is said that this injunction enjoins only the later time (*uttarakālatvam*) in the soma. There is another question raised here as to how does the suffix *ktvā* enjoin the later-time? On this it is said that, the meaning of the *ktvā* is the earlier-time and by *śakti* it gives out the same meaning. However, it is with respect to the soma sacrifice which is the *anuyogin* of the earlier time that it is said to enjoin the later-time in soma.

Observation

Thus we find through the above discussion that the suffix *ktvā* though accepted as denoting the earlier-time on the basis of the Pāṇinian rule *samānakartṛkayoḥ pūrvakāle*, is said to be enjoining order (*karma*) in certain sentences such as *vedaṁ kṛtvā vedīm karoti*. Also in the sentences such as *advaryugrhapatiṁ dīkṣayitvā brahmāṇaṁ dīkshayati*⁹...etc. While in other sentences such as *darśapūrṇamāsābhyām iṣṭvā soma yajeta* denoting the earlier time it enjoins the later-time with respect to the next element. Similarly, in *aśvinaṁ grahaṁ gr̥hitvā*...¹⁰etc it gives out the meaning as specific state of earlier-time (*pūrvakālatāviśeṣarūpam*) through secondary implication.

Conclusion

Through the above discussion, we find that the grammatical rules are just an indication of the meaning in which a particular element is used in the sentences. It is in

the domain of hermeneutics that various aspects which are made known under different circumstances of occurrences can be known. Thus, in order to know the import of an element in the language, a hermeneutical analysis is very important. *Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā* serves this very purpose. Such analysis shall not only broaden the view of understanding, but facilitate in other areas where application is prime such as rituals for Vedic literature and in computational linguistics where understanding import is necessary to accomplish artificial intelligence.

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- ³ कर्त्तरि कृत् Pāṇini's *Aṣṭādhyāyī* (P.) 3.4.67
- ⁴ P. 3.4.21
- ⁵ *Siddhāntakaumudī* (SK) 3320
- ⁶ समासेऽनन्पूर्वो क्तवो ल्यप् P. 7.1.37
- ⁷ *Āpastamba śrautasūtra* 7.3.10
- ⁸ *Taittirīya Saṁhitā* 2.5.6
- ⁹ *Śatapathabrāhmaṇa* 12.1.1.1
- ¹⁰ Unknown source